

The comparison of facilities and equipment safety of girls and boys prosperous and non-prosperous elementary schools of Hamadan

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was the comparison of facilities and equipment safety of girls and boys prosperous and non-prosperous elementary schools of Hamadan. The method of this research was descriptive and the statistical popularly was all elementary schools in Hamadan (N=125). Base on Morgan table, 90 schools were selected to this research with random stratified sampling method. Research made safety questionnaire was used to collect data.. Data analysis was performed by Shapiro Wilk test, one sample t-test and two-factor analysis of variance. The results showed that buildings and equipment for the schools of Hamadan in six components are weak. The hypothesis was tested using two-factor analysis of variance that the results showed there was no significant difference in the comparing the facilities safety and equipment. As well as, the results showed boys and girls schools interaction with prosperous and non-prosperous schools no significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Key Words: security, sport facilities and equipment, school, prosperous, non-prosperous

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